

ORGANIZATIONAL-METHOD OF INDIVIDUALIZATION OF HEALTH TRAINING FOR WOMEN

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Annotation: An individualized methodology for building health-improving aerobics trainings for women based on taking into account somatotypic features provided a statistically significant positive dynamics of indicators of physical development, body composition, functional state, physical fitness in the studied contingent of those involved in comparison with the initial values.

Key words: women, mature age period, somatotype, health improvement, aerobic programs, physical condition.

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ЗАНЯТИЙ ПО ФИЗИЧЕСКИЕ КУЛЬТУРЕ С ЖЕНЩИНАМИ РАЗНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Аннотация: Индивидуализированная методика построения оздоровительных тренировок по аэробике для женщин на основе учета соматотипических особенностей обеспечила статистически значимую положительную динамику показателей физического развития, состава тела, функционального состояния, физической подготовленности у исследуемого контингента занимающихся по сравнению с начальными значениями.

Ключевые слова: женщины, зрелый возрастной период, соматотип, оздоровление, аэробные программы, физическое состояние.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada turli yoshdagi ayollar bilan jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini tashkil qilishni takomillashtirish. Ularning jismoniy tarbiyasini takomillashtirishda somatotipik xususiyatlarni hisobga olgan holda ayollar uchun sog'lomlashtiruvchi aerobika mashg'ulotlarini takomillashtirishning individual metodologiyasi, jismoniy rivojlanish, tana tuzilishi, funktsional holati va jismoniy tayyorgarligi ko'rsatkichlarida dastlabki qiymatlarga nisbatan statistik jihatdan muhim ijobiy dinamikani ta'minlash haqida yozilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ayollar, etuk yosh davri, somatotip, salomatlikni yaxshilash, aerobik dasturlar, jismoniy holat.

Introduction. Fitness is a modern form of health-improving physical culture, which is now increasingly being introduced into the process of women's health improvement. An innovative variety of fitness areas increases the interest and introduces women of all ages to physical activity, provides them with the opportunity to choose fitness programs in accordance with their individual needs. The rapidly developing fitness industry is of interest to specialists in the field of health-improving physical culture for the scientific substantiation of the health-improving effectiveness of the most popular types of activities. Fitness as a social phenomenon unites women of different ages, levels of health and physical fitness, which indicates the need for a

deeper theoretical and experimental substantiation of various types of fitness focused on a mature contingent of those involved.

Literature review. The group form is currently one of the main ones in terms of the method of organizing and conducting classes in the field of sports and recreation services for the female contingent. In real practical conditions, group classes have both significant advantages and significant disadvantages [1, p 91.].

The analysis of scientific and methodological literature and practical activities made it possible to identify very conflicting opinions about the methodology of the group organization of the health-improving process of training for women. Today, the principle of variability has been proclaimed, which makes it possible for all participants in the physical culture and recreation process to choose, design and implement training programs according to their attractiveness and effectiveness, taking into account the interests, needs, age characteristics, and the level of the initial physical and functional state of women. One of the main requirements of the modern organization of the physical culture and health-improving process is to provide an individual approach to those involved [2, p 44.]. The problem of the scientific substantiation of the latter and the lack of modern systematized information about the adaptive reactions of the body of women of mature age to various motor influences served as the basis for the search for significant criteria for the individualization and differentiation of those involved in the aerobics system.

The purpose of the study: theoretical and experimental substantiation of an individual approach in the process of health-improving aerobic training with women of mature age [3, p 51.].

Materials and methods. In the course of the ascertaining experiment, a comprehensive diagnosis of the physical condition of women in the first period of adulthood who wish to engage in aerobics was carried out. According to the results of the study, a specific individualized direction of aerobic training effects for women was determined, taking into account their somatotypical features [4, p 66.].

Individualized aerobic health training programs were implemented by 48 women aged 21–35 years during a nine-month macrocycle. In accordance with the experimental individualized methodology, all women attended group classes 3 times a week for 60 minutes.

Analysis and results. Analysis of the initial level of physical development of the subjects made it possible to identify morphological indicators of various somatotypes. So, a distinctive feature of women with asthenic somatotype is the smallest values of the weight-height indicator, girth dimensions of the body, vital capacity of the lungs (VC). At the same time, hypersthene's have the highest values of these indicators. [5, p 26.] The differences are statistically significant for the 5% significance level. When comparing the indicators of the physical development of the subjects with the standard values, it was found that in asthenic women, the Quetelet index characterizes a body weight deficit by 2.68%, in normosthenic persons, on the contrary, this indicator is exceeded by 7.96% above the norm, in hypersthene representatives there is a maximum excess by 13.91%, which indicates the presence of overweight. As a result of the analysis of the indicators of the circumferences of the main parts of the body, low values of girth sizes are noted in asthenic women, and the average values characterize women of the normosthenic type. High values of this indicator were recorded in hypersthene individuals [6, p 348.].

The vital capacity of the lungs, which assesses the level of development of external respiration, is lower in asthenic persons by 13.07% compared to the proper one (according to the Ludwig formula), and in normosthenic and hypersthene women there is a decrease by 8.08 and 11.29%, respectively. An analysis of the initial indicators of body composition revealed that the percentage of the fat component in the body of women aged 21-35 ranges from 16.4 to 29.2%, while the optimal level of this indicator is in the range of 18-24%. Thus, in women of the asthenic type, a low indicator of the severity of the fat component is observed, normosthenic ones are at the upper limit of the optimal values, and a significant excess of the indicator is noted in hypersthene women. Similar variability can be traced in the analysis of the muscle

component in the subjects. The percentage of the muscle component in the body of women ranges from 29.3 to 44.4%, and normally this figure is 36–38% [6, p 350.].

Considering the main indicators of the cardiovascular system - heart rate at rest and blood pressure of the subjects, it can be noted that asthenic type individuals have a more economical and productive functioning of this system. The indicators of the respiratory system, assessed by the characteristics of VC, the Stange and Genchi tests indicate a higher oxygen supply to the body in normosthenic individuals. At the same time, the physical performance of women of the asthenic type is mostly satisfactory, while in normosthenic and hypersthenic women it is estimated as average. Comparative analysis of physical fitness indicators of the subjects also showed specific differences among representatives of different somatotypes. It was revealed that, in general, asthenic-type women have higher rates of coordination, speed and general endurance, a low level of development of flexibility and strength abilities.

Normosthenic type individuals have an average level of development of flexibility, strength of the muscles of the hand, strength endurance of the muscles of the abdomen, arms and shoulder girdle, general endurance and a low level of explosive strength of the muscles of the lower extremities, speed abilities and speed-strength endurance of the muscles of the arms and shoulder girdle. At the same time, hypersthenic women have above average flexibility, explosive strength of the muscles of the lower extremities and strength of the muscles of the hand, a low level of coordination, speed, strength endurance of the abdominal muscles, arms and shoulder girdle, speed abilities, speed-strength endurance [6, p 364.].

Conclusion/Recommendations. The results obtained in preliminary studies allowed us to establish the specifics of the individualized orientation of health-improving aerobic training for women of mature age in relation to their belonging to a particular somatotype and taking into account the characteristics of the morph functional state and physical fitness. Thus, the program for women of the asthenic type is aimed at increasing the girth sizes of individual parts of the body by increasing the muscle component.

Aerobic training included sets of exercises mainly of a power nature. The interval training method included five series of aerobic combinations (2–3 minutes each) with strength exercises (5–7 minutes).

The aerobics program for women of the normosthenic type is based on maintaining the existing level of physique due to an equivalent decrease in the fat component and a moderate increase in the muscle component. Aerobic training assumed a complex (equivalent) work of aerobic (20 minutes) and strength (20 minutes) orientation.

Complexes of power static-dynamic aerobic exercises provided for the isolated study of each individual muscle group in a certain order with a uniform distribution of the load on all muscle groups. For women of the hypersthene type, the aerobics program is aimed at reducing the girth dimensions of specific parts of their body by reducing the fat component and preserving the muscle. And aerobic training included sets of exercises predominantly of an aerobic nature.

FYV At the same time, women of the asthenic type have the opposite dynamics of changes: a significant increase in body weight by 2.3 kg was revealed due to an increase in fat and muscle mass, which indicates compliance with additional nutritional recommendations and specific training effects in order to increase body circumference .. As a result of the conducted pedagogical research, it was found that the morphological criterion - somatotype - is a significant and necessary condition for the individualization of the health-improving process by aerobics for women of mature age. Somatotype distinctive features in physical development, body composition, functional state, physical fitness of women of the first period of mature age were determined. The specific individualized direction of aerobic effects for representatives of each somatotype is specified. On the basis of taking into account the somatotypical characteristics of women aged 21–35 years, an individualized methodology for organizing health-improving aerobic training for them has been developed. Thus, an individually differentiated approach contributes to a more targeted management of the morph functional improvement of the body of women of mature age, the achievement

of an optimal level of their physical fitness. The effectiveness of the individualized health-improving method of aerobics is confirmed by a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) improvement in almost all fixed indicators that assess the functional state and physical fitness of women aged 21–35.

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